

ARCUS

ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM
OF THE UNITED STATES

2022 ANNUAL REPORT

Dear ARCUS Members and Colleagues,

During the past year, the global pandemic’s freeze on Arctic research community activities began a noticeable thaw. Old avenues of connection have reopened, allowing ARCUS to celebrate the completion of a number of long delayed activities in 2022, while also emphasizing how important it remains to continue working with each other in new ways.

Next year, ARCUS will be coming to the end of our current cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation. Over the next few months, ARCUS will be connecting with our funders, members, partners, and the wider Arctic research community to develop new ideas for programs and activities to meet the evolving needs of the Arctic research community.

This transition point marks a momentous opportunity to reimagine what support for Arctic research means in a world that has been forever changed by COVID and which will continue to face dramatic environmental and social disruption in the years to come.

In some ways, Arctic research has never been more connected than it is today. For many, collaboration opportunities are now only a virtual meeting or online conference away and programs dedicated to developing and maintaining diverse scientific communities are proliferating.

However, as the Arctic research community grows, so does the complex challenge of coordinating the myriad actors involved in the creation of new knowledge. Organizations like ARCUS and our Member Institutions continue to play a vital role by working together to reduce the many barriers to Arctic research exchange and cooperation that remain.

We are so grateful to the ARCUS staff, board, members, and partners for all their work to surmount these obstacles over the past year. As we look to the future, we invite you all to become more involved in these important community efforts— now is the perfect time to get involved!

Sincerely,

David M. Cairns
Board President, ARCUS

Helen V. Wiggins,
Executive Director, ARCUS

Cover photo credit: Photo by Adeena Teres (PolarTREC 2017), Courtesy of ARCUS

Report Content:

Pg 2: Strategic Goals & Objectives (2020-2025)
Pg 3: Staff
Pg 4: Board of Directors
Pg 5-6: Member Institutions
Pg 7: Partner Organizations
Pg 8: Committee Volunteers & Individual Members

Pg 9-10: ARCUS Cooperative Agreement Activities
Pg 11: Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook
Pg 12: Arctic Indigenous Partners & Scholars
Pg 13: Research Support Highlights
Pg 14: IRC Report & Early Career Awards
Pg 15: Other Forums, Meetings, & Events
Pg 16: Education Highlight: PolarTREC
Pg 17: Financial Report

STRATEGIC GOALS & OBJECTIVES (2020–2025)

Goal 1: Facilitate and Support Arctic Research Collaboration

- **Objective 1.1:** Provide Resources and Promote Innovative Practices for Collaborative and Interdisciplinary Research
- **Objective 1.2:** Connect and Support the Arctic Research Community Around Shared Topics of Interest
- **Objective 1.3:** Partner with Other Arctic Organizations to Catalyze and Broaden Networking Opportunities
- **Objective 1.4:** Promote Exchange, Collaboration, and Co-Production Between the ARCUS Community and US-Based Arctic Indigenous Community Members

Goal 2: Enhance the Effectiveness of Arctic Research Communication

- **Objective 2.1:** Increase Information Exchange and Knowledge Sharing Within the ARCUS Community
- **Objective 2.2:** Amplify and Share Arctic-Related Research, Knowledge, and Issues with Diverse Audiences
- **Objective 2.3:** Work with ARCUS Members to Prioritize and Address the Critical Needs of the ARCUS Community
- **Objective 2.4:** Build Awareness of and Cultivate Group Identity Between ARCUS, our Members, and our Partners

Goal 3: Educate K-16 Students and Formal and Informal Educators about the Arctic, and Engage them in Arctic Research

- **Objective 3.1:** Develop Professional Training Opportunities for Arctic Educators
- **Objective 3.2:** Champion Culturally Responsive Arctic Education and Outreach
- **Objective 3.3:** Foster Arctic Citizen Science and Community-Based Research
- **Objective 3.4:** Encourage Arctic Youth Involvement in Arctic Research Activities and Learning

Goal 4: Secure Resources to Support the ARCUS Mission

- **Objective 4.1:** Expand and Sustain a Diverse and Inclusive ARCUS Membership
- **Objective 4.2:** Strengthen ARCUS' Organizational Capacity
- **Objective 4.3:** Diversify ARCUS' Funding Sources
- **Objective 4.4:** Grow Reserves to Adapt and Respond to New Opportunities

ARCUS STAFF

Helen Wiggins
Executive Director
helen@arcus.org
Wasilla, AK

Brandi Austin
Director of Finance & HR
brandi@arcus.org
Fairbanks, AK

Kristi Weiss-Ackels
Accountant
kristi@arcus.org
Fairbanks, AK

B. Zeb Polly
Systems Administrator
zeb@arcus.org
Fairbanks, AK

Ronnie Owens
Information Technology Director
ronnie@arcus.org
Bellingham, WA

Judy Fahnestock
Project Coordinator
judy@arcus.org
Madbury, MA

Joed Polly
Video Production & Content Manager
joed@arcus.org
Somerville, MA

Stacey Stoudt
Project Manager
stacey@arcus.org
Anchorage, AK

Kuba Grzeda
Project Coordinator
kuba@arcus.org
Fairbanks, AK

Janet Warburton
Education Project Manager
warburton@arcus.org
Anchorage, AK

Betsy Turner-Bogren
Project Manager
betsy@arcus.org
Fairbanks, AK

Brit Myers
Project Manager
brit@arcus.org
Vashon, WA

Lisa Sheffield Guy
Project Manager
lisa@arcus.org
Pescadero, CA

ARCUS BOARD OF DIRECTORS

Audrey Taylor
University of Alaska Anchorage
artaylor@uaa.alaska.edu
Term End: 2022

David Cairns (President)
Texas A&M University
cairns@tamu.edu
Term End: 2022

Adrian Gall
ABR, Inc
agall@abrinc.com
Term End: 2022

Cheryl Rosa
US Arctic Research Commission
crossa@arctic.gov
Term End: 2022

Timo Koivurova
University of Lapland
timo.koivurova@ulapland.fi
Term End: 2022

Diane Hirshberg
University of Alaska Anchorage
dbhirshberg@alaska.edu
Term End: 2023

Kaare Erickson (Treasurer)
Ikaagun Engagement, LLC
sikuaq@ikaagun.com
Term End: 2023

Lauren Culler
Dartmouth College
lauren.e.culler@dartmouth.edu
Term End: 2024

Julie Raymond-Yakoubian
(Member-at-Large)
Kawerak, Inc.
juliery@kawerak.org
Term End: 2024

Canan Uluak Itchuaqiyak
Virginia Tech
canan@vt.edu
Term End: August 2024

Pips Veazey
University of Maine
alice.veazey@maine.edu
Term End: 2023

Stacey Fritz
Cold Climate Housing
Research Center/NREL
stacey.fritz@nrel.gov
Term End: 2024

Peter Webley (Secretary)
University of Alaska
Fairbanks
pwebley@alaska.edu
Term End: 2023

ARCUS MEMBER INSTITUTIONS

www.tamu.edu

Represented By:
David Cairns,
cairns@tamu.edu
Julie Loisel,
julieloisel@tamu.edu

www.unbc.ca

Represented By:
Stephen Déry,
stephen.dery@unbc.ca
Gary Wilson,
gary.wilson@unbc.ca

www.npolar.no/en

Represented By:
Nalân Koç,
nalan.koc@npolar.no
Ellen Øseth,
ellen.oseth@npolar.no

UArctic

www.uarctic.org

Represented By:
Arja Rautio,
arja.rautio@oulu.fi
Kirsi Latola,
kirsi.latola@uarctic.org

www.arctic.gov

Represented By:
Cheryl Rosa,
crosa@arctic.gov
John Farrell,
jfarrell@arctic.gov

www.virginia.edu

Represented By:
Matthew Jull,
mjull@virginia.edu
Howard Epstein,
hee2b@virginia.edu

www.en.uit.no/startside

Represented By:
Gunhild Hoogensen Gjorv,
gunhild.hoogensen.gjorv@uit.no
Marc Lanteigne,
marc.lanteigne@uit.no

www.tedstevensarcticcenter.org

Represented By:
Randy "Church" Kee,
randy.kee.1@us.af.mil
Matthew Schell,
matthew.schell.6@us.af.mil

www.uas.alaska.edu

Represented By:
Maren Haavig,
mmhaavig@alaska.edu
Charmaine Robinson,
cmrobinson7@alaska.edu

**Woodwell
Climate
Research
Center**

www.woodwellclimate.org

Represented By:
Robert Max Holmes,
rmholmes@woodwellclimate.org
Anna Liljedahl,
aliljedahl@woodwellclimate.org

www.uaa.alaska.edu

Represented By:
Diane Hirshberg,
dbhirshberg@alaska.edu
Thomas Ravens,
tmravens@alaska.edu

www.gml.noaa.gov

Represented By:
Brian Vasel,
brian.vasel@noaa.gov
Christine Smith,
christine.smith@noaa.gov

KAWERAK, INC.
www.kawerak.org

Represented By:
Melanie Bahnke,
contact@kawerak.org
Julie Raymond-Yakoubian,
juliery@kawerak.org

www.asu.org

Represented By:
Shauna BurnSilver,
shauna.burnsilver@asu.edu
Stephanie Pfirman,
spfirman@asu.edu

www.abrinc.com

Represented By:
Adrian Gall,
agall@abrinc.com
Gerald Frost,
jfrost@abrinc.com

www.gwu.edu

Represented By:
Robert Orttung,
rorttung@gwu.edu
Dmitry Streletskiy,
strelets@gwu.edu

www.aoos.org

Represented By:
Sheyna Wisdom,
wisdom@aoos.org
Holly Kent,
kent@aoos.org

www.uaf.edu

Represented By:
Nettie LaBelle-Hamer,
nettie.labellehamer@alaska.edu
Peter Webley,
pwebley@alaska.edu

www.arcticcentre.org

Represented By:
Timo Koivurova,
timo.koivurova@ulapland.fi
Stefan Kirchner
stefan.kirchner@ulapland.fi

www.uspermafrost.org

Represented By:
Ming Xiao,
mzx102@psu.edu
Michael Lilly,
mlilly@gwscientific.com

www.sitkascience.org

Represented By:
Lisa Busch,
lbusch@sitkascience.org
Naghham Sabah,
nsabah@sitkascience.org

www.dartmouth.edu

Represented By:
Melody Brown Burkins,
melody.b.burkins@dartmouth.edu
Lauren Culler,
lauren.e.culler@dartmouth.edu

www.nrel.gov

Represented By:
Aaron Cooke,
aaron.cooke.nrel.org
Stacey Fritz,
stacey.fritz@nrel.gov

www.worldwildlife.org

Represented By:
Alexis Will,
alexis.will@wwfus.org
Stephanie Lee,
stephanie.lee@wwfus.org

www.usm.maine.edu

Represented By:
Tracey Meagher,
tracey.meagher@maine.edu
Ross Hickey,
ross.hickey@maine.edu

www.washington.edu

Represented By:
Ed Blanchard-Wrigglesworth,
ed@atmos.washington.edu
Craig Lee,
craiglee@uw.edu

www.sandia.gov

Represented By:
Mark Ivey,
mdivey@sandia.gov

www.whoi.edu

Represented By:
Carin Ashjian,
cashjian@whoi.edu

www.rutgers.edu

Represented By:
Åsa Rennermalm,
asa.rennermalm@gmail.com

www.umaine.edu

Represented By:
Pips Veazey,
alice.veazey@maine.edu

ARCUS PARTNER ORGANIZATIONS

Eskimo Walrus Commission

The Eskimo Walrus Commission partners with ARCUS to produce the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO). SIWO is a resource for Alaska Native subsistence hunters, coastal communities, and others interested in sea ice and walrus.

Association of Polar Early Career Educators (APECS)

ARCUS and APECS have a Memorandum of Understanding that acknowledges the joint commitment of both organizations to the professional development of early career polar researchers. Additionally, APECS serves as a partner in the Early Career Travel Awards.

Anchorage Museum

The Anchorage Museum and others have partnered with ARCUS to host the Anchorage Arctic Research Summit.

National Weather Service - Alaska Region

The National Weather Service - Alaska Region partners with ARCUS to produce the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO).

Alaska Native Science & Engineering Program (ANSEP)

ARCUS partners with ANSEP by serving as a host to ANSEP Summer Bridge students (high school graduates) or Fellows (undergraduate students).

Alaska Natural Resource & Outdoor Education Association (ANROE)

ARCUS and ANROE have a Memorandum of Agreement that establishes a partnership to collaborate on the development and delivery of natural resource education content and resources.

Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC)

ARCUS administers NSF funding to the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee's secretariat. Additionally, ARCUS works with the IARPC secretariat to support research initiatives emerging from IARPC Collaboration Teams.

Inuit Circumpolar Council - Alaska (ICC-Alaska)

ICC-Alaska is a co-lead with ARCUS on the Arctic Indigenous Scholars Program, which creates opportunities for Indigenous scholars to educate and inform policy- and decision-makers in Washington, DC. Additionally, ARCUS detailed a staff member to ICC-Alaska to forge stronger partnerships and add capacity at the hosting organization.

Smithsonian Arctic Studies Center

The Smithsonian Arctic Studies Center provides D.C. host support for the ARCUS Indigenous Scholars Program.

Polar Educators International (PEI)

ARCUS provides in-kind secretariat support for PEI, which is an international professional network for everyone who educates in, for, and about the polar regions.

Learn More: <https://www.arcus.org/arcus/partners>

COMMITTEE VOLUNTEERS & INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS

ARCUS is deeply grateful to the many individuals who supported our efforts in 2022 through countless volunteer hours, membership dues, & active participation in ARCUS programs and events!

INDIGENOUS SCHOLAR HOSTS

Tony Dearman	Cordelia Qigñaq Kellie	Sarah Pease
Roberto Delgado	Bre Klayum	Nancy Shorey
William Fitzhugh	Igor Krupnik	Xoco Shinbrot
Julian Guerrero	Stephen Loring	Kelley Uhlig
Angela Hernandez	Jennifer Mercer	Felicia Wright

SIWO ADVISORY COMMITTEE

Hajo Eicken	Gay Sheffield	Michael Lawson
Matthew Druckenmiller	Jill Prewitt	Melissa Kreller
Igor Krupnik	Sheyna Wisdom	
Brad Benter	Richard Thoman	
	Mary-Beth Schreck	

ARCUS MEMBERSHIP COMMITTEE

Adrian Gall	Emily Maxwell	Heather Sauyaq Jean
Stacey Fritz	Ming Xiao	Gordon
Brit Myers	Asa Rennermalm	Helen Wiggins
Audrey Taylor	Kelley Uhlig	

EARLY CAREER AWARD COMMITTEE

Lavanya Ashokkumar	Claire Griffin	Julie Loisel
Josephine-Mary Sam	Jiake Zhou	Stacey Stoudt
Lisa Sheffield Guy		

POLARTREC ADVISORY COMMITTEE

Regina Brinker	Janet Warburton	Gary Wesche
Sarah Crowley	Judy Fahnestock	Marilyn Sigman
Dieuwertje Kast	Dominique Richardson	Alex Eilers

BOARD NOMINATING COMMITTEE

David Cairns	Peter Webley	Pips Veazey
Canan Uluak Itchuaqiyag		

2022 ARCUS INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS

Muhammad Asaduzzaman	Thian Yew Gan
Michael Ashley	Amanda Gavin
Rebecca Atwood	Mary Gibbons
Eda Ayaydin	Katherine Ginsbach
Jean E. Balestrery	Dave Grant
Carolina Behe	Suzanne Green
Dylan Blaskey	Lenore A. Grenoble
James Bradley	Gabriella Gricius
Bridget Burger	Karen Grosskreutz
Joshua Butterick	Emre Hakguder
Timothy Cabalo	Joyanne Hamilton
David Cairns	David Harning
Seth Campbell	Matt Heavner
Manwei Chan	Saskia Hirsch
Matthew Clay	Diane Hirshberg
Ethan Conley	Hannah Holland-Moritz
Roger Creel	Robert Hollister
Peppi Croft	Kaisa Holloway Cripps
Cansu Demir	Karl Fred Huemmrigh
Sandra Derendy	Lissa Hughes
Somayajulu Dhulipala	Canan Uluak Itchuaqiyag
Craig Dorman	Acacia Johnson
Janet Duffy-Anderson	Cody Johnson
Helena Edelson	Sarah Johnson
Hajo Eicken	Patricia Johnston
Kaare Sikuag Erickson	Jessica Kantarovich
Itorobong Etuknwa	Edward Kaufmann
Renato Fakhoury	Randy Kee
Erica Ferencik	Kabiraj Khatiwada
Eric Filardi	Ekaterina Kim
Craig Fleener	Lauren Kipp
Stacey A. Fritz	Madison Kluge

INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH COMMITTEE

Holly Hapke	Liz Weinberg	Caitlyn Wylie
Mia Bennett	Helen Wiggins	Peter Webley
Martin Jeffries	Pips Veazey	Gisele Arruda
Brit Myers	Kuba Grzeda	Karl Huemmrigh
	Canan Uluak Itchuaqiyag	
	Julie Raymond-Yakoubian	

Timo Koivurova	Savannah Peery	Steven Snell
Ben Kopec	Ernie Petit	Madeline Snigaroff
Stanislav Ksenofontov	Lori Petrauski	Armina Soleymani
Kyle Lambert	Oleg Pokrovsky	Mason Stockstill
Millie Lambert	James Powell	Angela Szesciorka
Steven Lamy	Mindy Price	Audrey Taylor
Kathryn Lavelle	Maryam Rahnemoonfar	Katherine Todd
Michelle Leclair	Julie Raymond-Yakoubian	Nathalie Triches
Olivia Astillero Lee	Kristen Reece	Maria Tzortziou
Daniel Leifson	Katherine L. Reedy-Maschner	Muhammad Kaleem ul Fateh
Dawn Marie Lemke	Keith Reimink	Stephen Vavrus
Peng Lian	Jessica Rich	Pips Veazey
Julie Lina	Michelle Ritchie	Danielle Verna
Lorene Lynn	Rolf Rødven	Kaiyuan Wang
Michelle Mack	Anna Russell	Zhaojun Wang
Gaurav Madan	Misa Saros	Matthew Wee
Bruce Main	Sara Saastamoinen	Michael Weintraub
Emily Maxwell	Asad Sabbah	Vincy Winifred
Hilary McMahan	Katherine Schexneider	Ramey Wood
Jessie Meyer	Jennifer Schmidt	Ming Xiao
Victoria Miles	Forrest Schoessow	Shamsudeen Yekeen
Jessica Miller	Alicia Sendrowski	Leonid Yurganov
Murielle Nagy	Monika Sikand	Laura Zanotti
Kimberly Ohnemus		Frank Zhu
Ashok Pandey		

ARCUS COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT

Building Community in Arctic Research: Communication, Research Support, and Multi-Knowledge System Integration

An NSF-funded Cooperative Agreement (2019–2023; Award # OPP-1928794) supports the work we do to nurture collaborations across disciplines, sectors, and perspectives; and to broaden participation across the Arctic research enterprise.

ARCUS Cooperative Agreement activities focus on:

- Research community support, including fostering community-driven research initiatives through virtual tools and support of early-career researchers;
- Networking activities, including network analysis and community-building events for the Arctic research community;
- Collaboration with Indigenous communities and knowledge systems, including integration of Indigenous knowledge with weather and ice predictions, and support for Indigenous scholars of all career levels;
- Arctic research communications and outreach; and
- Support of the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC).

The added value of these research support functions—effective collaboration management, networking, communications, and outreach—is key to successful interdisciplinary research.

WHAT KINDS OF ACTIVITIES DOES THE COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT SUPPORT?

Arctic Community Networking

Arctic Indigenous Scholars Program

Early Career Conference Awards

Arctic Citizen Science Virtual Conference

Research Incubation Activities

Communications Tools

Alaska Native Organization Partnerships

Arctic Research Seminar Series

Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook

Arctic Research Day Events

COMMUNITY CONNECTIONS

COOPERATIVE AGREEMENT ACTIVITIES (Year 3 of Award: September 2021–August 2022)

Mailing Lists

- ArcticInfo: 5,296 subscribers, 298 postings, emails opened 189,264 times
- Polar Education List: 1,682 subscribers, 60 announcements

Witness the Arctic Newsletters

- 8,781 subscribers
- 39 articles from 66 contributors
- 35,642 webpage views

ARCUS Community Meetings & Events

- Arctic Research Speed Networking - 58 participants
- Arctic Research Webinars - 6 seminars with 362 participants from 24 countries and 36 US states
- Event Video Archive - ARCUS recordings during the reporting period were viewed 5,315 times
- Funders Meet & Greet - 117 attendees with 8 featured funding organizations
- ARCUS Annual Meeting* - 120 attendees & 21 ARCUS Institutional Members represented

* The ARCUS Annual Meeting is not supported by the Cooperative Agreement.

Website

www.arcus.org

- 272,968 page views and 160,385 unique visitors
- 46% users from US and rest from 209 different countries
- Arctic Calendar with 3,460 events and 37,985 page views
- Publications Directory - 127 publications with 1,389 page views
- Directory of Arctic Researchers with 4,176 Arctic experts

HOW TO JOIN THE ARCUS COMMUNITY ONLINE:

- 1) Subscribe to [ArcticInfo](http://www.arcus.org/arctic-info) for weekly news from the broader Arctic research community. This is a place to submit your event announcements, job openings, & other news: www.arcus.org/arctic-info
- 2) Subscribe to the [Witness The Arctic](http://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic) newsletter to receive more in-depth articles highlighting Arctic research & education efforts: www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic
- 3) Subscribe to the [ARCUS Monthly Report](http://www.arcus.org/member-newsletter) to receive a monthly update on ARCUS & ARCUS Member Organization news as well as a digest of job openings, professional development opportunities, and funding opportunities: www.arcus.org/member-newsletter.
- 4) Submit your Arctic-related meetings, events, & funding deadlines to the [Arctic Calendar](http://www.arcus.org/events/arctic-calendar): www.arcus.org/events/arctic-calendar
- 5) Subscribe to the [Polar Education Mailing List](http://www.polartrac.com/about/education-list) for education-related news & announcements.: www.polartrac.com/about/education-list
- 5) Join the [Directory of Arctic Researchers](http://www.arcus.org/researchers): www.arcus.org/researchers
- 4) Join us on [Social Media](#):

@ArcticResearch
@PolarTREC

@ArcticResearchConsortium
@Polar.TREC
@SealceForWalrus

Company: ArcticResearch
Group: Sea Ice Prediction Network

Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook

The Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO) is a resource for Alaska Native subsistence hunters, coastal communities, and others interested in sea ice and walrus. The SIWO provides weekly reports each spring with information on weather and sea ice conditions relevant to walrus in the northern Bering Sea and southern Chukchi Sea regions of Alaska.

More information:
www.arcus.org/siwo

Follow us on Facebook:
www.facebook.com/seaiceforwalrus

LOCAL OBSERVERS:

Shishmaref:
Curtis E. Nayokpuk

Wales:
Robert Tokeinna, Jr.

Brevig Mission:
Marcus Barr

Gambell:
Clarence Irrigoo, Jr.

Savoonga:
Aqef Waghiyi

Diomede:
Eeleengayouq Ozenna

Nome:
Frank (Boogles) Johnson

SIWO is managed by ARCUS and produced in partnership with the National Weather Service, Eskimo Walrus Commission, University of Alaska Fairbanks, and local observers. Support for SIWO is provided by the National Science Foundation's Arctic Sciences Section (PLR-1928794).

of Weekly Reports in 2022 (March-June)

14

of local observations

59

Alaskan communities engaged

43

of Facebook Followers

2,091

The 2022 SIWO season ran from 25 March–24 June. A new partnership with the Alaska Ocean Observing System has been established to bring additional Bering Sea data on surface currents into SIWO reports. ARCUS also partnered with the Arctic Elder Society to test the SIKU app for SIWO observer use. An evaluation of SIWO is now underway in partnership with University of Alaska Fairbanks, funded by Alaska Sea Grant.

Walrus resting on ice near Gambell, AK in May 2022. Photo by Clarence Irrigoo, Jr.

2022 Arctic Indigenous Partnerships

- ARCUS supported a 1-year full-time staff detail to the Inuit Circumpolar Council (ICC) Alaska to support information & data archiving.
- ARCUS partnered with ICC Alaska to manage the Indigenous Scholars Program. Three scholars traveled to meet with policymakers in Washington, DC this fall.
- ARCUS provided staffing support for the ICC Alaska workshops to develop the "Protocols and Guidelines on the Equitable and Ethical Engagement of Inuit and Indigenous Knowledge".

- ARCUS partners with the Eskimo Walrus Commission to produce the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO). SIWO is a resource for Alaska Native subsistence hunters, coastal communities, and others interested in sea ice and walrus.

- ARCUS hired an ANSEP student to support ICC Alaska's data & archiving project.

- ARCUS supported a full-time Indigenous staff detail to the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee to support Indigenous engagement activities.

- ARCUS partnered with the Arctic Eider Society established to test the SIKU app for Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook observer use.

2022 Arctic Indigenous Scholars

2022 Arctic Indigenous Scholars visit Washington, DC. From left to right: Naidene Beachler, Richard B. Slats, Kimberly Pikok.

ARCUS and the Inuit Circumpolar Council Alaska serve as co-leads for the Arctic Indigenous Scholars Program. The objective of the program is to create a space for Indigenous scholars to educate and inform policy- and decision-makers on Arctic issues

Three Arctic Indigenous Scholars were selected in 2020 by a seven-member volunteer selection committee. Their trip to Washington DC, originally scheduled for May 2020, was delayed due to COVID related travel concerns until fall 2022. The three scholars traveled to Washington, DC to meet with decision and policy-makers in September 2022.

Naidene Beachler - Naidene is a Mental and Behavioral Health Coordinator with the Matanuska-Susitna Borough School District where she provides services district-wide. The focus of her policy-maker engagement is on reducing Alaska's suicide mortality rates through mental health services in education.

Richard B. Slats - Richard is a Cup'ik from Chevak, Alaska appointed to the North Pacific Fisheries Management Council's Fisheries Ecosystem Plan Task Force. The focus of his policy-maker engagement is climate change, mining, tribal rights, and subsistence hunting.

Kimberly Kivvaq Pikok - Kimberly is an Iñupiaq from Utqiagvik, Alaska and an Interdisciplinary Studies graduate student at the University of Alaska Fairbanks. The focus of her policy-making engagement is ensuring Indigenous perspectives inform all aspects of research and decision-making.

2022 RESEARCH SUPPORT HIGHLIGHTS

ARCUS regularly serves an important facilitation role for collaborative research endeavors seeking to engage participants across institutions, sectors, disciplines, cultures, geographic locations, and/or career levels.

Sea Ice Prediction Network - Phase 2 (SIPN2)

SIPN2 activities aim to improve Arctic sea-ice forecasts using a multidisciplinary approach that includes modeling, new products, data analysis, and scientific networks.

- ARCUS' role in SIPN2 (funded by NSF) includes strategic planning, project management, networking, and outreach & communications.
- A key activity of SIPN is the Sea Ice Outlook, with reports in June, July, and August containing a variety of perspectives on Arctic sea ice—from observations of current conditions, to advanced numerical models, to qualitative perspectives from citizen scientists. In 2022, 118 predictions were contributed to the effort by groups from around the world.

More information: <https://www.arcus.org/sipn>

Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee

In 2022, ARCUS served as the fiscal administrator for the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) Secretariat.

- ARCUS' role with the IARPC (funded by NSF) includes receiving and administering funds for the secretariat, grant reporting, contract development and administration, and other administrative duties.
- ARCUS staff also partner with IARPC secretariat staff to co-host programs and support large meetings and events.

More information: <https://iarpccollaborations.org>

Interdisciplinary Research Committee Report

The ARCUS Interdisciplinary Research Committee was an ad-hoc committee established in 2021 by the ARCUS Board of Directors to discuss interdisciplinary research in the context of wider Arctic research programs and initiatives; identify challenges; and explore existing collaborative research programs, tools, and resources.

The committee report, released in 2022, synthesizes the committee's discussions as well as their recommendations for specific actions to increase the capacity of the wider Arctic research community to productively undertake collaborative, co-produced, and convergence research.

More information:

https://www.arcus.org/files/publication/33258/2022_arcus_interdisciplinary_research_committee_report.pdf

Early Career Conference Funding Awards

This ARCUS Early Career Conference Funding Award supports the participation of US-based, early career researchers in meetings and events relevant to Arctic research, with a focus on underrepresented minorities (Black, Indigenous, and People of Color; BIPOC).

"This was very beneficial for me. As an early career academic, associated conference fees are often suddenly higher than what I was familiar with as a PhD candidate. The support helps address this change and allowed me to attend a conference that I otherwise might not have. I made some really meaningful connections at the conference. Thank you!"

More information: <https://www.arcus.org/early-career-funding>

Congratulations To:

Victoria Bergstrom (Providence College)
Alicia Blanton (Jackson State U.)
Julio Cenicerros (U. Texas at El Paso)
Haley Cynar (Oregon State U.)
Tanea Fisher (Jackson State U.)
Richterica Ford (Jackson State U.)
Thomasina Horton (Jackson State U.)
Saravanan Kanagaratnam (Texas Tech U.)
Rajesh Kandel (Vanderbilt U.)
Lauren Kipp (Rowan U.)
Margaret Lindeman (UC San Diego)
Cameron McMillan (U. of Toledo)
Grant Peel (U. Hawaii at Manoa)
Lydia Schoeppener (U. of Notre Dame)
Kharis Schrage (MIT)
Emma Robertson (Penn State)
Stanislav Ksenofontov (U. Northern Iowa)
Zoe Mercurieff (U. Alaska Fairbanks)
Harmony Wayner (AK Sea Grant Fellow)
Onema Adojoh (Case Western Reserve)

Other Forums, Meetings, & Events

Polar Technology Community Forum

In 2022, ARCUS staff worked with the organizing committee of the 2020 Polar Technology Conference to convene regular meetings of the Polar Technology Community. The community was hosted as a self-forming team on the IARPC Collaborations website and was co-led by Lisa Sheffield Guy (ARCUS), Mark Seefeldt (CU Boulder), and Jonathan Blythe (BOEM). Over 59 forum members joined the team for monthly presentations and discussions on various polar technology related topics.

U.S. - Canada Cross-Border Research Panels

Association of
Canadian Universities
for Northern Studies

In late 2021, ARCUS collaborated with the Association of Canadian Universities for Northern Studies (ACUNS) to convene two panel discussions focused on enabling cross-border research collaborations between the United States and Canada.

UArctic North American Members Event

In June, ARCUS staff co-hosted with UArctic's Academic Vice-President Diane Hirshberg (University of Alaska Anchorage) and UArctic's Vice-President of Northern Community Engagement Sheila Downer (Memorial University of Newfoundland) the first gathering of UArctic's North American Institutional Members as part of the 2022 UArctic Assembly meeting in Portland, Maine. The event convened US and Canadian UArctic representatives to discuss expanding opportunities for North American collaboration in Arctic research and education.

UArctic

National Park Service Beringia Days

In 2021, ARCUS staff began working with the National Park Service on plans to host the next Beringia Days International Conference during August 2023. Stay tuned for this unique heritage event!

EDUCATION HIGHLIGHT

Since 2004, ARCUS has been supporting teacher-researcher collaborations. To date, there have been over 180 educators that have had the unique opportunity to work with scientists in the polar regions. Currently supported through the "STEM at the Poles! Research Experiences for Formal and Informal Educators in the Polar Regions" grant from the National Science Foundation (Award# 1918637), this program invigorates polar science education and understanding by bringing educators and polar researchers together through field-based, hands-on, research experiences in both the Arctic and Antarctica.

Deployments to the Arctic resumed this summer, sending Sarah Johnson to the Arctic Ocean with the International Arctic Buoy Program, Erin Towns to Greenland with Dr. Sarah Das, Eric Filardi to interior Alaska, and Rebecca Siegel to the Bering, Chukchi, and Beaufort seas with a team from WHOI led by Donald Anderson. Antarctic expeditions are also now underway for Lucy Coleman, Elaine Krebs, and Bill Henske. For the latest news on the program or to follow the PolarTREC teachers on their expeditions, please visit the PolarTREC Virtual Base Camp online at www.polartrec.com.

More information: <https://www.polartrec.com>

2020-2022 PolarTREC Cohort

Erin Towns

Jon Pazol

Tammy Orilio

Cassie Kautzer

Sarah Johnson

Bill Henske

Jenn Heidrich

Kathy Ho

Elaine Krebs

Liza Backman

Eric Filardi

2022 FINANCIAL REPORT

Fiscal Year 2022 Revenue by Source (October 2021–September 2022)

NSF Cooperative Agreement #1928794 (38.7%)	\$	672,424
NSF Cooperative Agreement #1928794 for IARPC Secretariat (48.4%)	\$	840,353
PolarTREC (7.3%)	\$	126,187
PolarTREC-UAF Subaward (0.8%)	\$	14,357
PolarTREC-Miami U. Contract (0.03%)	\$	600
SIPN2 (0.9%)	\$	16,398
SEARCH (0.9%)	\$	14,780
The Arctic in the Classroom (0.1%)	\$	1,967
NPS Beringia Days (0.3%)	\$	5,390
NPRB Curriculum & Education Directory (0.7%)	\$	12,681
AK Sea Grant-UAF/SIWO (0.1%)	\$	982
ARCUS Unrestricted Funds (1.7%)	\$	29,501

www.arcus.org